

Review Article

A brief account on COVID-19

Pinky Sultana ^{1*}

¹ School of Pharmacy, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai, China

***Corresponding Author**

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Abstract: COVID-19 is a novel coronavirus, a pathogen that has caused a pandemic with an outbreak in Wuhan in Hubei province of China in late December of 2019. It belongs to Betacoronavirus genera and shares similarity with SARS-CoV & MERS-CoV. It consists of a single stranded RNA genome which is comparatively larger than other family viruses. Its origin is known to be from bats. It is transmitted from human to human via droplets or close contact and has incubation period of 2-14d. Symptoms are generally fever, cough and fatigue for mild cases, however it progresses to multi organ dysfunction, pneumonia, acute respiratory distress syndrome and even death. Asymptomatic people are also considered as potential transmitters. The virus has spike glycoproteins (S) that gains entry to the host cells by binding to receptors Angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2). Till now no drugs have shown promising results, and efforts are being made for a fast development of therapeutics. This review briefly describes the impact of COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: COVID-19, ACE2, SARS-CoV-2

Introduction

Coronavirus is a pathogen that causes respiratory and gastrointestinal tracts infections. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus SARS-CoV and Middle East Respiratory syndrome coronavirus MERS have been previously reported as a great public health threat. SARS-CoV2 or COVID19 emerged in Wuhan city of Hubei province in China during December 2019 and has since created a pandemic around the world(Wang, Horby et al. 2020). On Jan 30,2020 WHO declared Covid19 as Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC). Until today, May 20,2020 worldwide cases have been approx. 5 million and 325,214 deaths(Worldometers). Coronavirus belongs to the family Coronaviridae and are enveloped positive single stranded RNA viruses with genomes size ranging from 26 to 32 kb. Among the four genera it belongs to

Betacoronavirus and shares 70% genome similarity to SARS-CoV (Hui, E et al. 2020). Ge et.al have reported a whole genome sequence from two Chinese horseshoe bats and found two novel bat coronavirus that showed similarity with SARS- CoV-2 suggesting that it may have originated in these bats (Ge, Li et al. 2013). Coronavirus ranges from 60nm to 140nm in diameter and poses spike like projections on its surface resembling a crown; thus its name Coronavirus.(Richman DD 2016). In 2002-2003 SARS-Coronavirus affected 8422 people in China with 11% mortality rate and in 2012 the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus MERS exploded in Saudi Arabia and affected 2492 people with 34% mortality rate (World Health Organisation , Chan-Yeung and Xu 2003). Thus giving an idea about the deadly novel coronavirus. This review gives a brief note on how COVID19 has become one of the fatal Virus of the century.

How did COVID-19 originate?

The end of December 2019 occupied major number of patients in hospitals with signs of severe pneumonia of unknown etiology among adults in Wuhan, Capital of Hubei Province in China. A common link for majority of cases identified a wet Wholesale Seafood Market located in Huanan where wild and live animals was being traded. With the rising health severity, all of the patient's epithelial airway (respiratory tract) samples were examined. On January 1st 2020, the seafood market was shut down by Wuhan public health authorities and China reported to World Health Organization about the outbreak. 7th January 2020, the virus is now identified as novel coronavirus and named 2019-nCov, the new coronavirus in 2019, by WHO (Wang, Horby et al. 2020) (Zhu, Zhang et al. 2020). The virus was characterized by next generation sequencing and Real time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT- PCR). Experts of the Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) reported that the virus has stemmed from the animals in the market and the environmental samples of the market were tested positive. It was later confirmed that 2019-nCov can transmit from human to human. 23rd January,2020, the time of Chinese spring festival that allows mass migration of people was halted by suspending public transport resulting a complete lockdown Wuhan. By this time cases from other countries emerged as they reported of being a returnee from Wuhan. On 30th January, World health Organization (WHO) declared COVID-19 (officially named as of February) a Public Health Emergency of International Concern and that we are under an Epidemic. By the End of February almost more than 80,000 cases were confirmed worldwide with Hubei Province solely possessing 77,000 cases. On 11th March 2020, WHO declared COVID19 as a pandemic.

Following two months, in 20 May 2020, the current center of global coronavirus disease is none other than The United States with exponential rise of cases up to 1,593,093 with total of 94,949 deaths followed by Russia with 317,554 cases and 3,099 deaths. COVID-19 has given worldwide public health catastrophe(The 2020).

Why COVID-19 resulted into a Pandemic?

Epidemiology & Pathogenesis

Currently the count of confirmed cases has hit the mark of 5 million over the globe and continues to rise. Live updates are accessible on WHO, CDC, and John Hopkins websites. Any age group and race is susceptible to this infectious disease. The largest number of infected cases has commenced from The United States jeopardizing millions of lives. This virus spreads from person to person via droplets (cough, sneeze, etc.) when in close contact with symptomatic and asymptomatic individuals. It can survive in different surfaces for prolonged time period, in air it can spread up to 1-2meter, however it gets easily destroyed by common disinfectants (Kampf, Todt et al. 2020, Rothe, Schunk et al. 2020). COVID-19 patients have thought to be key source of spreading infection; apparently asymptomatic patients may also be a potential source of infection. In addition, it is quite appalling, as recovered COVID19 patients have shown positive RT-PCR test results, this is remarkably different when compared with SARS or MERS and in the history of human(Lan, Xu et al. 2020). The median incubation period of COVID-19 is 5.1 days, and onset of symptoms after exposure is reported up to 14 days(Lauer, Grantz et al. 2020). COVID-19 cases have different effects: asymptomatic (1.2%) and can recover in 1-2 weeks, mild pneumonia (80.9%); severe cases (13%); critical cases (4.7%); and deaths (2.3%)(Rothe et al. 2020).

COVID-19 is an enveloped pathogen containing a single stranded RNA genome which is in association with a nucleoprotein within in the capsid, this capsid is buried inside phospholipid bilayer. Glycoproteins (S) protrudes through the envelope giving spikey projection on the outer surface, it also consists of Hemagglutinin-esterase protein (HE). As shown in Figure1, COVID19 is very similar to other Betacoronavirus. Among the spike (S) protein in the viral envelope the membrane (M) protein and the envelope (E) protein are also located However, in comparison with other coronavirus, it contains the largest RNA genome size of 26-32 kb with 30-40% G+C content. COVID-19 has 5' (269nt) and 3' (229nt) terminal sequences and gene order 5'-ORF1aS-E-M-N-3'. Small ORFs are located between these conserved genes (ORF1ab, S (3822nt), E (228nt) , M (669nt), N (1260nt)) and downstream of nucleocapsid gene in different lineages of the virus(Woo,

Huang et al. 2010) (Khailany, Safdar et al. 2020). M protein shows of higher interest as it spans three times around the membrane with a short amino terminal outside and long carboxy terminal outside the virus. Mutations in the luminal, transmembrane, amphiphilic, or carboxy terminal domains impairs the M assembly on the envelope(de Haan, Kuo et al. 1998).

Fig1 . Schematic representation of a Coronavirus/COVID-19.

Entry and replication-

COVID-19 predominantly transmits via respiratory droplets, close contact and fecal-oral routes. Initially it replicates in mucosal epithelium in nasal cavity and pharynx followed by larger rates of proliferation in the respiratory tract and gastrointestinal mucosa(Xiao, Tang et al. 2020). To gain entry Coronavirus uses S protein and is primed by protease enzyme known as TMPRSS2 to completely gain the entry into cells. It binds to the angiotensin- converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor present in the host (human). ACE2 gets downregulated leading overproduction of angiotensin II and in return angiotensin II stimulates type 1a receptor eventually enhancing lung permeability and pathology Upon entry into the host cells, viral RNA genome uncoats and ORF gets translated following replication, budding via endoplasmic reticulum/Golgi apparatus and finally released via plasm membrane fusion (de Wit, van Doremalen et al. 2016, Hoffmann, Kleine-Weber et al. 2020). ACE2 is equally distributed in nasal mucosa, bronchus, lung, heart, esophagus, kidney, stomach, bladder, ileum and others, providing an exposure to COVID19 easy

attack(Zou, Chen et al. 2020). Non- respiratory symptoms such as heart and liver injury, kidney failure and diarrhea have reported suggesting COVID19 can arrange a multiple organ involvement for its survival. A clinical report suggested an alarming fertility concern in young males has aroused as the virus has significant risk on the testicular tissues.

Clinical Manifestation- Are symptoms limited?

Symptoms appears after median incubation period of 5.2 days(Li, Guan et al. 2020). The time of onset of symptoms ranges between 6-41 days, shorter in those of more than 70 years of age and longer for those below 70 years. A common spectrum of symptoms upon infection ae usually fever, cough, fatigue and others include headache, sputum production, diarrhea, lymphopenia (Carlos, Dela Cruz et al. 2020, Wang, Tang et al. 2020). CT findings on chest revealed pneumonia including acute respiratory distress syndrome, RNAemia, acute cardiac injury and several secondary infections (Huang, Wang et al. 2020). However, it cannot be neglected the fact that asymptomatic states have also been reported as potential transmitter (Bai, Yao et al. 2020). Progression to pneumonia and respiratory failure associates with cytokine storming (arise in IL2, IL7, ILL10, GCSF, IP10, MCP1, MIP1A, and TNF α)(Chen, Zhou et al. 2020). As mentioned earlier, virus induced ACE2 downregulation and antibody dependent enhancement (ADE) causes uncontrolled pulmonary inflammation. Once pulmonary ACE2 function is lost, renin –angiotensin system (RAS) is deeply affected leading to more vascular permeability. Patients producing antibodies at early stages, experiences long term inflammation, ARDS, and sudden death. Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), is severe as it blocks the entry of oxygen into lungs and blood circulation(Thompson, Chambers et al. 2017). Of about 34 genes have been reported to be linked ARDS, of which ACE2, IL10, TNF, VEGF showed valuable biomarker and may explain molecular sites for possible treatments of ARDS(Meyer and Christie 2013).

Therapeutics and prevention

No vaccine for COVID-19 is available at present, as WHO estimates 18 months for development of a vaccine. Patients with severe symptoms are given either oxygen therapy or mechanical ventilation. WHO guidelines for treatment addresses several ways for identifying and segregating patients depending on their conditions. Supportive treatment also includes renal replacement therapy (CRRT), extracorporeal membrane oxygen (ECMO). None of the antiviral drugs showed any effects up until now. Antiviral drugs such as Ribavirin (SARS-CoV, Hong Kong), Ritonavir (HIV), Remdesivir (MERS-CoV), Nelfinavir, Arbidol, Chloroquine may be considered as

potential therapeutics with regards of their history on successful inhibition of other coronaviruses. Among these, Chloroquine may be of an interest as it is effectively inhibited SARS-CoV-2 *in vitro* (Wang, Cao et al. 2020) and have been since recommended for clinical treatment. Apart from drugs, Convalescent Plasma has been broadly recommended with a restriction of patient's stage of illness(Li, Wang et al. 2020). Some of the properties of this virus such as asymptomatic transmission, prolonged incubation, conjunctiva, long duration of illness, infectivity over onset of symptoms, and being tested positive even upon recovery has been a barrier for a complete prevention. Isolating oneself and maintaining distance of one meter, use of surgical masks have been recommended for practicing to avoid the virus. Diagnosis are carried out by several systems such as Nucleic Acid Test (use of RT-PCR), CRISPR/Cas13 (was used to test Zika Virus), Serologic Diagnosis and Imaging Technology (CT).

COVID-19 – Impact on Obesity, Diabetes

Obesity

Obesity may be on of the risk factor as it has shown an exponential vulnerability to infections. Immune system itself plays a significant role in obesity induced adipose tissue inflammation, which in turn causes metabolic dysfunction, hypertension and cardiovascular disease. H1N1 is a key example where obesity plays an independent risk factor. In addition, patients with obesity having Influenza A sheds virus longer than those without obesity. A clinical study in Wuhan with COVID-19 infected patients, showed 88.2% of patients who did not survive had BMI > 25kg/m² whereas 18.9% of survivors possessed only BMI 22.0kg/m². As it is now known that ACE2 is important for the virus, the level of ACE2 is relatively higher in adipose tissues than lungs. Treatments with anti- hypertension medications for obese people have higher chances of enhancing the expression of ACE2 and resulting into more vulnerability to the virus(Kassir 2020).

Diabetes

Diabetes to be an independent risk factor for COVID-19 remains unclear and evidences are controversial. The 2009 H1N1, SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV reported diabetes and uncontrolled glycaemia in the non- survivors. A high level of stress in diabetic patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 have been witnessed with rising expressions of hyperglycemic hormones. around 10% Type2 Diabetes patients suffering from COVID-19 in Wuhan exhibited a state of hypoglycemia. Hyperglycemia is linked with defective immunity. Influenza infection significantly rises at high glucose concentrations *in vitro* which indicates hyperglycemia may assist in viral

replication(Hussain, Bhowmik et al. 2020). However, some predictions suggest patients with DM have higher susceptibility for binding to the virus, longer duration for viral shedding, weak levels of T cells, higher cytokine syndrome and prevalence of cardiovascular disease. Administration of insulin causes higher level of ACE2 production. A Mendelian study depicted a relation of DM with increased lung ACE2 level. Therefore, it is more likely that DM patients may contribute to severity in infection (Muniyappa and Gubbi 2020).

Fig 2 A) Possible pathway of Renin Angiotensin system In COVID-19 patient.
B) Susceptibility of Obese and Diabetic COVID-19 Patients.

As shown in Fig2 A) The Renin angiotensin system in a COVID-19 Patient is impaired. The S-protein of COVID-19 binds to the receptor ACE2 of the host cell and downregulates it restricting it to convert Angiotensin II into Angiotensin and promotes vasoconstriction causing lung dysfunction. B) In obese patients, Adipose tissues consists of great amount of ACE2 thereby making it readily available for COVID-19 entry. As hyperglycemia occurs more insulin is administered into the diabetic patient and this causes rise in the level of ACE2, allowing easy susceptibility.

Conclusion

Currently, COVID-19 pandemic has grown uncontrollable and has since jeopardized millions of lives. We are devoid of specific COVID-19 treatment, since its emergence it has spread its way to every single country and is growing at a faster rate. Efforts are being made for developing therapeutics, trials of human drug compounds, and Vaccines. With deeper knowledge on the basis

of its pathogenicity and its special features that distinguishes it from other coronaviruses, it is possible to discover a way for treatment or prevention.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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